

Environmental Carcinogenesis: Nitric Oxide Release after Photodecomposition of Nitrosocontaminants in Drugs (Under UV Exposure) as Substantial Factor for Skin Carcinogenicity. Sertraline Induced Cutaneous Melanoma - Third Reported Case in Scientific Literature

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Abstract

The modern understanding of carcinogenicity has increasingly shifted towards the recognition of the importance of some new triggering factors or factors with exogenous nature. The early and adequate recognition of the environmental carcinogenic acting agents seems to be of paramount importance for their subsequent fast elimination. The regular, permanent intake of nitrosamines in drugs seems to be one of the most serious problems worldwide concerning the problem with the environmental mediated carcinogenicity. The reason for that is that the so called Nitroso compounds seems to be 1) genome modifiers and 2) photocarcinogens. Recent molecular insights suggest that certain nitroso compounds present in widely used medications worldwide may play a more significant role in carcinogenesis than genetic predisposition or other triggering factors alone. There are two main mechanisms that may explain the potential link or axis between the onset of depression and the development and progression of cutaneous melanoma: 1) current concepts of depression pathogenesis define it as an additionally inflammatory disorder characterized by the dysregulation of cellular immunity (immunity, responsible also for protection from cutaneous melanoma), and 2) the environmental exposure to human photocarcinogens, the so-called nitrosamines, through medications that undergo photodecomposition under ultraviolet light, acting as nitric oxide donors. In this context, we aim to emphasize the potential carcinogenic impact of even a monomedication while integrating the latest emerging evidence. We report the third case report of sertraline-induced cutaneous melanoma in a patient with a diffuse metastatic spread. The concepts of Nitroso-Photocarcinogenesis/ Photo-Nitrosocarcinogenesis - also referred as drug-mediated Nitrosogenesis or Oncopharmacogenesis / Pharmacocarcinogenesis - represent one of the most compelling emerging paradigms in modern medicine, particularly with regard to skin cancer and melanoma pathogenesis.

More Information

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Introduction

It is well documented that cancer patients are at increased risk of developing psychiatric disorders, most frequently adjustment disorders with depression [1]. The presence of such conditions is often associated with delayed diagnosis and treatment initiation, which may consequently reduce long-term cancer survival rates by 10% to 20% [1].

However, the reverse relationship also warrants consideration - can panic attacks and depression precede a cancer diagnosis, or do they merely contribute to diagnostic delay? Environmental psychological factors can modify and trigger an organic response [2]. Depressive disorders may represent a potential risk factor in oncogenesis, contributing to both initiation and progression of the disease [2].

Modern explanations about psychophysiological mechanisms linking depression and cancer progression include dysregulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, particularly disturbances in the diurnal variation of cortisol and melatonin [3]. Moreover, depression can impair components of immune function, thereby influencing the body's ability to maintain effective cancer surveillance [3].

Because the depression-cancer axis appears bidirectional, one must consider whether oncogenesis associated with depressive disorders might, in part, be related also to the medications used to treat those disorders - in particular, whether they contribute to an increased risk of malignancy such as cutaneous melanoma and how.

Recent studies and reports have begun to explore this hypothesis, integrating molecular findings on the depression-cancer axis [4] with clinicopathological correlations that support the concept of drug-induced carcinogenesis [5,6].

The presence of photocarcinogenic compounds such as the nitrosamines in certain antidepressant medications is no longer a purely hypothetical concern, as emerging studies have begun to establish a correlation between these agents and the skin carcinogenesis [5,6]. Moreover, such substances could be probably considered as potential triggers - and possibly even initial causative factors - in the development or progression of skin cancer [5,6].

Following the newly emerging literature supporting the depression-cancer axis, and considering the third documented case of sertraline-induced advanced stage IV malignant melanoma presented by our team, we aim to discuss a potentially novel perspective integrating both molecular and clinicopathological correlations within the context of nitrosamine-induced skin carcinogenicity in the context of the drug intake.

Case Report

A 54-year-old male presented to the dermatology department with a primary complaint of a tumor formation on the right side of the trunk, present for 3-4 years, which has shown significant growth in recent years.

The patient has a 10-year history of panic attacks with depressive episodes, managed with sertraline 50 mg once daily. He also reports arterial hypertension, atrial fibrillation and flutter, for which he has recently (2-3 days prior to the consultation/intensive care unit) been prescribed the following medications: torasemide 10mg once daily in the morning, amlodipine/valsartan 5/160mg once daily in the evening, bisoprolol 5 mg once daily in the morning, amiodarone hydrochloride 200 mg twice daily for two weeks, and dabigatran etexilate 150mg twice daily.

Due to the impaired general condition, the most significant blood tests from the formation point of view were: elevated WBC $11.7 \times 10^9/l$ (normal range $3.5-10.5 \times 10^9/l$), decreased RBC $3.14 \times 10^{12}/l$ ($4.4-5.9 \times 10^{12}/l$), decreased HGB 95.0 g/L (135-180 g/L), decreased HCT 0.28 L/L (0.4-0.53), increased unmatured granulocytes $3.98 \times 10^9/l$ ($0.0-0.05 \times 10^9/l$), decreased lymphocytes 12.0% (20-40%), increased sediment rate erythrocytes 50 mm/h (0-20 mm/h), increased INR 3.08 (0.8-1.3), increased aPTT 2.63 (0.8-1.3), increased D-dimer 2.70 microgr/ml (0.0-0.500 microgr/l), increased triglycerides 4.0 mmol/L (0.08-1.7 mmol/L), increased glucose levels 7.81 mmol/L (3.8-6.1 mmol/L), increased creatinin levels 124.3 micromol/L (53-114.9 micromol/L), increased urea 22.7 mmol/L (2.8-8.3 mmol/L), increased uric acid 550 micromol/L (220-450 micromol/L), increased total protein levels 61.0 g/L (64-83 g/L), decreased albumin 33 g/L (35-50 g/L), increased ASAT 74.0 U/L (11-34 U/L), increased ALAT 170.0 U/L (0-45 U/L), increased GGT 380 IU/L (0-55 IU/L), increase alkaline phosphatase 213.0 IU/L (40-150 IU/L), increased LDH 1023.0 U/L (125-220 U/L), increased CRP 246.3 mg/L (0-5.0 mg/L), and increased kalium 5.7 mmol/L (3.5-5.6 mmol/L).

Dermatological examination revealed a tumor-like formation located in the right abdominal region, measuring approximately 15 cm x 10 cm, prominent above the skin surface, with central atrophy, intermittent bleeding, and a foul odor. The lesion was clinically suspicious for achromatic melanoma (Figure 1). Multiple small nodular formations of small caliber were noted adjacent to the primary lesion, raising suspicion for satellite metastases.

Figure 1: A Tumor-Like Formation Located in the Right Abdominal Region, Measuring Approximately 15 cm x 10 cm, Prominent Above the Skin Surface, with Central Atrophy, Intermittent Bleeding, and a Foul Odor

The lesion is clinically suspicious for achromatic melanoma (Figure 1).

Due to mild respiratory failure identified during hospitalization, oxygen therapy at 3 l/min via nasal cannula was initiated. A chest X-ray was performed, revealing findings suspicious for disseminated metastasis. Laboratory results showed marked leukocytosis and an LDH exceeding 1000 U/L, suggestive of possible tumor necrosis. Empiric antibiotic therapy with amoxicillin/clavulanic acid 1.2 g three times daily for 7 days was started, later replaced by the pulmonologist with Piperacillin/Tazobactam administered three times daily.

Due to slightly elevated renal retention parameters, a nephrology consultation was obtained. To prevent contrast-induced nephropathy, the nephrologist recommended infusion of water-salt solutions up to 1.5 l-2 l, with diuresis monitoring, along with single dose of sodium bicarbonate 8.4% 20 ml i.v. and acetylcysteine 200 mg per os according to the prescribed regimen.

During the inpatient stay, a contrast-enhanced whole-body CT scan was performed to determine the stage of the suspected tumor. The findings were indicative of extensive metastatic involvement, including the lungs, liver, and lower gastrointestinal tract. A necrotic right

level 5a lymph node was identified, along with left-sided pleural effusion. Multiple focal pulmonary lesions, and infiltrative changes in the left lower lobe. Additional findings included right axillary, mediastinal, right bronchopulmonary, and abdominal lymphadenopathy; a tumor formation involving the skin and subcutaneous tissue of the right; secondary hepatic lesions; and anodule in the left adrenal gland, likely representing either ametastasis or an adenoma. Further findings included calyceal microlithiasis in the right kidney and possible obstruction of the colon.

Regarding the cutaneous tumor, several biopsies were obtained and submitted for histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis. The histopathological examination revealed a fragmented specimen represented by diffuse epidermal necrosis bordering on irregular acanthosis, underlying proliferation of atypical cells with pronounced nuclear polymorphism and bright cytoplasm forming a conglomerate with cytological discohesion, infiltrating the deep dermal compartments, reaching the hypodermis (Figs. 2-3).

Figure 2: Epidermal Necrosis Diffuse Proliferation of Melanoma Cells with Severe Nuclear Atypia x HE x 40

Figure 3: Melanoma Cells Exhibiting Severe Polymorphism, Atypical Mitosis and Diploidy x 100 x HE

Histology panel: diffuse epidermal necrosis bordering on irregular acanthosis, underlying proliferation of atypical cells with pronounced nuclear polymorphism and bright cytoplasm forming a conglomerate with cytological discohesion, infiltrating the deep dermal compartments, reaching the hypodermis (Figure 2 and Figure 3). Immunohistochemically, the tumor cells showed 100% positivity for SOX-100 (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Sox-10 Positivity of the Melanoma Cells

Immunohistochemically, the tumor cells showed 100% positivity for SOX-100 (Figure 4). The lesion corresponded to Clark level IV with a Breslow thickness greater than 4mm, showing evidence of lymphovascular invasion and ulceration. The histopathological findings were consistent with ulcerative nodular melanoma, stage IV(pT4bN3M1c).

Due to elevated CRP levels and paraclinical evidence of severe pulmonary inflammation in the context of the underlying disease, pulmonology consultation was obtained. Based on the recommendations, methylprednisolone 20 mg i.v. twice daily, Ademetionine i.v. twice daily, and intravenous sodium chloride (1.5l over 24 hours) were added to the treatment regimen before the CT scan.

Due to active bleeding from the tumor formation, intravenous 0.9% sodium chloride and three ampoules of Etamzilate i.v. were administered additionally, resulting in successful hemostasis.

Due to the described findings from the CT scan and suspicion of subileus (in an asymptomatic patient), an urgent surgical consultation was requested. Abdominal ultrasound revealed multiple lesions in the liver, and aerocolic intestinal loops, with no evidence of an acute surgical abdomen. It was recommended to continue outpatient management, including a liquid diet (broths, soups, kiwi, honey) and active clinical monitoring.

Because of a tachyarrhythmia absoluta during hospitalization, the patient was transferred to the intensive care unit for short-term monitoring and management. Electrical cardioversion was performed,

followed by optimization of the previously initiated antiarrhythmic therapy with amiodarone hydrochloride. An outpatient tapering regimen was prescribed for the subsequent two weeks: 200 mg three times daily for 7 days, followed by 200 mg twice daily for 7 days, and thereafter continued as maintenance therapy with 200 mg once daily.

After receiving the microbiological results of the sputum culture, which identified *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ss. *Pneumoniae* and *Candida albicans*, fluconazole 200 mg once daily i.v. was added to the treatment regimen, in combination with amoxicillin/clavulanic acid administered three times daily at 8-hour interval in an outpatient setting.

Due to suspected stage IV disease with disseminated metastases involving the brain and bones, outpatient contrast-enhanced cranial CT, bone scintigraphy, and serum S-100 were recommended, followed by BRAF mutation analysis to evaluate eligibility for targeted therapy with BRAF/MEK inhibitors and/or immunotherapy (oncology unit). The patient was subsequently referred to the oncology department for further management and treatment planning.

Discussion

Facts and controversies have long surrounded the relationship between anxiety and depressive disorders [7]. In a study by Stein et al [7], 63 patients meeting the DSM-III-R criteria for panic disorder were evaluated, with 40 patients (63%) experiencing at least one major depressive episode during their lifetime. Interestingly, 32.5% of these patients experienced their first depressive episode prior to the onset of panic disorder, 37.5% after the onset, and 30% concurrently [7]. Furthermore, patients with a longer duration of illness, early-onset depression, or a family history of anxiety or depression were at an increased risk of recurrent depressive episodes [7].

In recent years, depression has been traditionally associated with imbalances in neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine [8]. Emerging evidences, however, highlights a strong link between depression and immune system dysregulation, suggesting that its pathophysiology is more complex and not yet fully understood [9].

In a study by Gao et al [4], patients with depression compared to healthy controls demonstrated a significant decrease in CD8 T cells, cytotoxic cells, T cells, T helper cells, Tgd, and Th2 cells, alongside increased levels of dendritic cells and neutrophils. Immune pathway analyses revealed increased antimicrobial, chemokine, cytokine, and TNF family member activities, with reduced TCR signaling in depression patients [4]. The key immune-related gene and potential diagnostic marker for depression, CD3G, was found to be critical: low CD3G expression in

depression was associated with enhanced immune response and activation of inflammatory pathways [4]. Notably, in numerous cancers, CD3G is upregulated and correlates with immune cell infiltration and activation of oncogenic pathways [4].

Elevated inflammation in depression is associated with reduced responsiveness to antidepressant therapies, highlighting the need for improved treatment strategies [10]. This pro-inflammatory state can also activate oncogenic pathways [4], suggesting that chronic immune dysregulation in depression may not only impair therapeutic efficacy but also increase the risk of subsequent cancer development.

A recent review by Cao et al [11] highlighted the bidirectional relationship between depression and cancer, identifying chronic inflammation - mediated primarily by IL-6, TNF-alpha, and IL-1beta - as a key physiological link.

Depression can dysregulate the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, disrupt in gut microbiota, and provoke immune imbalances, creating a systemic pro-inflammatory state that further potentiates oncogenesis via activation of critical signaling pathways, including JAK-STAT3, NF-kB, MAPK, and PI3K/AKT, which drive tumor proliferation, angiogenesis, immune evasion, and metastatic behavior [11].

The overall biological mechanisms - primarily the dysregulation of neuroendocrine and immune-inflammatory pathways - establishing a complex cycle through which major depressive disorder accelerates tumorigenesis and disease progression are driven by metabolic reprogramming (promoting tumor proliferation and progression), sympathetic activation (through norepinephrine release binding to adrenergic receptors on tumor cells and further fueling tumor progression via the IL-6/STAT3 signaling axis), and inflammation with epigenetic regulation (mediated by hyperactivity of the HPA axis and the subsequent release of pro-inflammatory cytokines that enhance tumor cell survival) [11-13].

An interesting observation was reported by Mössinger et al [14], where patients with depression demonstrated an 18% increased overall risk of cancer diagnosis, with the highest risks observed for lung cancer (HR: 1.39 [1.21-1.60], $p < 0.0001$), gastrointestinal cancers (HR: 1.30 [1.15-1.46], $p < 0.0001$), breast cancer (HR: 1.23 [1.12-1.35], $p < 0.0001$) and urinary cancers (HR: 1.23 [1.06-1.43], $p < 0.01$).

A chronic inflammatory microenvironment promotes the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) [15]. They can disrupt cellular signaling pathways, induce DNA damage, and promote genomic instability, thereby enhancing the survival and progression of malignant cells [15].

The expression of nitric oxide synthases (NOSs), particularly inducible NOS (iNOS), results in sustained production of nitric oxide (NO) - a potent mutagenic carcinogen leading to persistent nitrosative stress [15]. Notably, iNOS expression has been documented in approximately 60% of human metastatic melanoma cases and is associated to poorer survival outcomes [15-16]. iNOS expression has been found to be elevated in melanoma cells, with its levels increasing proportionally with advancing Clark stages of melanoma [17-18]. Moreover, iNOS appears to play a critical role in the early transition of localized melanoma within the skin to a metastatic lesion [17-18].

The precise mechanism by which nitrosative stress modulates p53 (a tumor suppressor protein) activity remains unclear; however, endogenous NO in melanoma has been shown to induce S-nitrosylation (SNO) of p53, resulting in functional inactivation of the protein [15].

According to the article by Grigoruta et al [15] low-level nitrosative stress may stimulate melanoma cell growth, while high-level nitrosative stress impair significantly cell viability in a dose-dependent manner.

Studies suggest that NO exerts a dual effect on melanoma, either suppressing or promoting tumor progression [19].

NO and its metabolites influence multiple aspects of melanoma biology, including proliferation, metastasis, immune modulation, autophagy, and apoptosis [19]. Nitrates and nitrites represent end products of NO metabolism [19].

Nitrosation (nitrosylation) is a term used for the incorporation of a nitric oxide (NO) group onto another molecule with an alkene bond between the N and O [17,20].

The NO group can attach to the nitrogen atom of an amine - typically a secondary amine, resulting in the formation of an N-nitrosamine (R₂N-NO) [21]. Many nitrosamines are recognized human carcinogens and can be found widely in the environment, including in air, water, foods, drinks, and drugs [21].

Of particular interest in the medical field is the emerging concern of nitrosamine contamination in widely used medications. New concepts such as Nitrosogenesis, Nitroso Photocarcinogenesis/Photo Nitrosocarcinogenesis of skin cancer, and Oncopharmacogenesis are already increasingly being recognized as the new scientific reality that could not be ignored anymore [22-23].

Nitroso - contamination - such as with NDEA, NMBA, and NDMA - can occur exogenously in drugs or form de novo under certain conditions, including drugs secondary or tertiary amines, acidic gastric environment, and the presence of nitrite-rich foods [22,24].

Secondary or tertiary amines may indeed represent potential risk factors for skin cancer in humans [25]). According to a study by Tomozane et al [26], nitrosoproline - a phototoxic and photocarcinogenic compound - exhibits dose-dependent genotoxicity following UVA exposure prior to metabolic activation, concurrently leading to the release of nitric oxide, a well-established procarcinogenic mediator.

Cancer development is strongly associated with chronic inflammation, where nitric oxide reacts with reactive oxygen species (ROS), producing mutagenic and carcinogenic effects that contribute to the development of melanoma, as well as breast and colon cancer [27].

From these observations, it can be concluded that nitrosamines in drugs could act as nitric oxide (NO) donors after: 1) absorption into the human body, 2) deposition on skin and subsequent 3) photodecomposition after exposure to UV radiation [25].

This mechanism underscores their significant procarcinogenic potential, representing a global health concern given their widespread presence in medications [25].

The liver and gut microbiota play a crucial role in the metabolism of these nitrosamines, determining their systemic availability and subsequent (photo) carcinogenic potential [25].

Although polymedication intake could theoretically elevate nitrosamine contamination by introducing additional contaminants/ polycontamination, in practice, certain drugs are disproportionately affected [28].

Some medications are more “prone” to nitrosamine contamination, and the FDA now classifies drugs according to their carcinogenic potential [28].

Of particular interest is N-nitroso-sertraline, a nitroso compound detected in the antidepressant sertraline [28], which is commonly prescribed for conditions such as panic disorder, social anxiety disorder and major depressive disorder [29].

N-nitroso-sertraline is currently under potency category of 2 with recommended AI limit of 100 ng/day [28].

Although the FDA classifies sertraline with a carcinogenic potency of 2 [28], there are already reports linking severe oncological outcomes to its long-term use, as documented in two separate case reports of sertraline-induced melanomas [22,30]. According to the official FDA bulletin, the drug classified under carcinogenic potency of 2/NDSRIs exhibits a similar carcinogenic potency comparable - if not nearly identical - to that of N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA) [22,28].

NDMA, in particular, has been shown to induce tumor formation in the liver, gastrointestinal tract, lungs, and

kidneys through direct activation of RAS oncogenes [31]. A nitrosamine can have multiple carcinogenic effects, both prior to and following metabolic processing [31], as well as photodecomposition in the skin before metabolic activation in the liver [26].

Observing the clinicopathological correlations raises the question of whether the official regulatory statements accurately reflect the risk - or if the true extent of nitrosamine contamination may be substantially underestimated.

Photosensitivity and phototoxicity associated with antidepressant use, including sertraline, have been documented in the literature [32,33].

However, the general concept remains - cumulative nitroso-mediated photo-toxicity can ultimately lead to nitroso-mediated photocarcinogenicity, particularly in the development of skin cancer such as cutaneous melanoma [22,31].

The two previous case reports documented melanoma development at earlier stages [22,30]. However, our case being - the third reported - resulted in a fatal outcome: long-term systemic intake of sertraline led to the terminal stage IV disseminated melanoma. This “nightmare” underscores a broader clinical concern - contaminated medications must be urgently addressed and eliminated.

In addition to sertraline, other antidepressants - including amitriptyline, bupropion, citalopram, clomipramine, desipramine, desvenlafaxine, escitalopram, imipramine, nortriptyline, proprylone, and venlafaxine - are also identified on the FDA list of nitroso-contaminated medications, each exhibiting different carcinogenic potency [28].

Contrary to the statement that nitric oxide can serve as a mediator protecting the skin function [34], the development of yet another case of drug-induced skin cancer - specifically melanoma - raises an important contradiction. Such observations should prompt critical thinking from every clinician when evaluating the available data.

In the future, therapeutic strategies could focus on targeting of the pro-inflammatory component within this vicious cycle. Promising approach involve targeting nNOS to enhance the anti-melanoma activity of immune checkpoint inhibitors while also regulating the tumor microenvironment [35].

Conclusions

The concept of drug-mediated Nitroso Photocarcinogenesis/Photo Nitrosocarcinogenesis encompasses two primary mechanisms: 1) immune suppression or dysregulation, consistent with current literature characterizing depression as an inflammatory disorder, affecting at that way the immunity, responsible for protection from cutaneous melanoma from one side, and second: 2) the impact of environmental carcinogenic compounds on the human

genome, notably through the intake or endogenous formation of nitrosamines during drug intake.

Regardless of whether the bidirectional relationship between the depression and melanoma development is fully understood, the possibility for drug-induced melanoma progression and aggressive metastatic behavior underscores the urgency of addressing this issue.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethics Statement

Ethics approval statement is not required.

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